

PREPARATION OF ANION EXCHANGERS SELECTIVE FOR COPPER AND MOLYBDENUM IONS

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Abstract. A novel method for obtaining an anion exchanger through the polycondensation of furfural with melamine and formaldehyde (DFA) has been developed. The properties and structure of the synthesized anion exchanger were studied using a combination of elemental analysis, physicochemical methods, as well as alkalometric and potentiometric titration, mass spectrometry, IR spectroscopy, thermogravimetry, and photolorimetry. The main physicochemical and chemical characteristics of the anion exchangers – such as sorption of copper, nickel, molybdenum, and other ions, the degree of dissociation of ionogenic functional groups, and others – were investigated. Correlations between the chemical composition of the initial monomers, their sorption and physicochemical properties, and the characteristics of the resulting anion exchangers were established, demonstrating the potential for producing ion exchangers that can serve as import substitutes.

Keywords: furfural, melamine, diphenylamine, anion exchanger, sorption, polycondensation, ion exchange polymer, wastewater treatment, sustainable development.

Introduction

Nowadays, the rapid development of industry, the resolution of environmental problems, and the production of competitive and environmentally friendly products increasingly require the implementation of modern technologies. In recent years, the introduction of innovative approaches and new developments has significantly increased the production volume and quality of industrially essential products. In this context, the use of chemically active substances for the efficient purification of wastewater through the synthesis of cation exchangers and anion exchangers, as well as the improvement of their physicochemical and sorption properties, is of particular scientific and practical importance. These technologies not only contribute to environmental protection but also enhance resource efficiency, product quality, and safety in industrial processes. Thus, the development of cation and anion exchangers and the enhancement of their properties represent a crucial stage in the advancement of modern industrial and ecological technologies.

Worldwide, the development of ion-exchange polymers, including anion exchangers, for the selective recovery of rare and valuable metal ions from industrial wastewater is of significant scientific and practical importance. This involves expanding the raw material base for their production and scientifically substantiating the corresponding solutions. In particular, it is necessary to determine the chemical composition, physicochemical properties, and sorption characteristics of the initial raw materials suitable for the synthesis of ion-exchange polymers; to obtain a weakly basic anion exchanger with complex-forming and selective sorption properties through the polycondensation of furfural with melamine and formaldehyde (DFA); and to identify the optimal conditions for anion exchanger synthesis, including the effects of reaction temperature,

the ratio of initial components, and the concentration of catalysts on the properties of the resulting anion exchanger [1–4].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, theoretical and practical results are being achieved in the development and implementation of technologies for producing cation and anion exchangers based on local raw materials for the purification of industrial wastewater. The third direction of the “Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” emphasizes the critical task of developing high-tech industrial processing sectors, primarily through the deep processing of local raw material resources, to produce high-quality finished products. In this context, conducting scientific research on the production of new ion-exchange anion resins from local industrial waste is of particular importance.

The aim of the study is to obtain complex-forming anion exchangers through the polycondensation of furfural with melamine and diphenylamine, and to apply them for the removal of metal ions from wastewater in the chemical and hydrometallurgical industries.

To achieve this aim, the following tasks were carried out:

- determination of the chemical composition, physicochemical properties, and sorption characteristics of the initial raw materials suitable for the synthesis of ion-exchange polymers;
- synthesis of a weakly basic anion exchanger with complex-forming and selective sorption properties toward colored and rare metal ions (copper, molybdenum, etc.) through the polycondensation of furfural with melamine and formaldehyde (DFA);
- identification of the optimal conditions for anion exchanger synthesis and investigation of the effects of reaction temperature, the ratio of initial components, catalyst concentration, and other parameters on the properties of the resulting ion-exchange anion;
- development of the anion exchanger production technology and characterization of the obtained ion-exchanger in terms of physicochemical and sorption properties, including the sorption of copper, nickel, molybdenum, and other ions, sorption capacity, and the degree of dissociation of functional groups.

Figure 1. Change in the logarithm of the concentrations of the reactants during the reaction at different temperatures: 1 – 130°C; 2 – 120°C; 3 – 110°C.

In order to obtain an anion exchanger with high thermo-chemical stability, mechanical strength, and selective properties toward molybdenum ions, furfural was used instead of formaldehyde as the crosslinking agent in the synthesis. The formation patterns of the anion-

exchange polymer through the polycondensation of furfural with melamine (DFA) were investigated. The presence of aromatic units (DFA) together with the heterocycles of furfural in the anion exchanger structure significantly enhances its chemical, thermal, and mechanical stability [5].

To ensure uniform polycondensation, the reaction was carried out in solvents such as ethanol, isoamyl alcohol, and dimethylformamide (DMF), among others. The highest polymer yield was observed when ethanol and DMF were used. When one part by weight of solvent and one part by weight of melamine were applied, the polycondensation proceeded uniformly, resulting in an anion exchanger with sufficient exchange capacity and good mechanical strength. The kinetics of the polycondensation reaction between melamine and furfural was studied at 100°C, 110°C, 120°C, and 130°C, with a constant molar ratio of melamine to furfural of 1.5:1.0. The experimental results are presented in Figure 1.

In calculating the reaction rate constant from the change in furfural concentration, it is suggested that polymer formation occurs through the interaction between the carbonyl group of furfural and the reactive hydrogen atoms of the melamine amino groups. In the first stage of the reaction, the formation of methylol derivatives is taken into account [6].

In the substitution of both hydrogen atoms of the amine, dimethylol derivatives can be formed.

The methylol derivatives formed in this way begin to interact with each other by releasing water and forming cross-links that connect individual amine molecules. The experimental results are consistent with the IR spectroscopic studies of the initial substances. It was found that the degree of change in polymers at different temperatures depends on the duration of the process. Based on these results, the logarithmic dependence of the concentration of the reacting substances on time at various temperatures was determined. For the calculations, results corresponding to a degree of change not exceeding 30% were used. As can be seen from Figure 1, the linear relationship along the $\frac{1}{a-b} \ln \frac{(a-x)b}{(b-x)a} - \tau$ axis indicates that this process corresponds to reactions described by a second-order equation [7–8].

The temperature dependence of the rate constants follows the Arrhenius equation. The activation energy of the melamine–furfural polycondensation reaction, determined from the lg k versus 1/T plot, was found to be 98 kcal/mol. The effect of the initial substance ratios on the polycondensation process was studied. The dependence of the reaction rate constant on the furfural concentration showed that at 120 °C, the increase of the rate constant with the furfural concentration in the reaction medium is linear. Thus, based on the results of the conducted study, the optimal conditions for the reaction were determined as follows: T = 120 °C, DMF as the medium, and a furfural-to-melamine molar ratio of 2.0:1.0. The properties of the obtained anionite are presented in Table 1.

The individual patterns of ion exchange in the synthesized anionite have been studied, and they can serve as a basis for the physicochemical characterization of the synthesized anionite.

Physicochemical investigation of anionites allows identifying ways to modify certain properties of the ionites. The properties of the obtained anionite were compared with those of industrial anionites AN-31, AN-2F, and FAN anionite, which is based on furfural and polyethylene polyamine. Additionally, industrial anionite AN-1, which contains a triazine ring in its structure, was used [9].

Table 1

Main physicochemical properties of anionites

Indicators	Unit of measur e-ment	Anionite based on melamine, furfural, and diphenylamine	FBG anionite based on benzoguanidine and furfural	FDG anionite based on diphenylamine and furfural	AN-1 anionite based on melamine and formaldehyde
Moisture	%	-	-	-	15
Static exchange capacity (SEC) for 0.1 N solutions of: Sodium chloride Hydrochloric acid Nitric acid Sulfuric acid	g/ml	0,6	4,8-5,0	6,5-7,2	0
		4,5-5,0	4,6	6,2	3,96
		5,08	4,5	6,3	4,17
		5,95			4,95
Capacity of the swollen anionite in OH ⁻ form	ml/l	1,6-1,8	2.8	3.8	2,5
Chemical stability. Static exchange capacity (SEC) in 0.1 N HCl solution after boiling the anionite for 30 minutes in: 5 N NaOH 5 N H ₂ SO ₄	mg-eq/l	4,5	4,5	6,3	-
		4,2	4,6	6,4	-
Thermal stability. Static exchange capacity (SEC) in 0.1 N HCl solution after boiling the anionite in water for 20 minutes	mg-eq/l	4,8-5,0	4,7	6,4	-

Sorption of molybdenum ions and ammonium molybdate mixture with 1 N Na₂SO₄ solution (C_{initial} = 1 g/l, pH = 4.5–5)	mg/g	206	354	200	165

One of the main indicators that determines the physicochemical properties of ions is the exchange capacity, which is usually determined using 0.1 N solutions of mineral acids found in industrial solutions. Table 2 presents the exchange capacities of anionites obtained by various methods.

Table 2

Exchange capacity of the obtained anionite

Anionite	Functional groups of the anionite	Exchange capacity, mg-eq/g			pK _o ^H
		Theoretical	Static	Calculated based on N%	
	-NH ₂ -NH ₃ -N=	5.3	5.5	5.3	8.3

As can be seen from Table 2, the total capacity of the anionite determined by various methods is almost the same.

*Figure 2. Dependence of anionites' exchange properties on the pH environment:
 1 – AN-31; 2 – FAN; 3 – synthesized anionite*

In this study, the ion-exchange capacity of the obtained anionite was also investigated in relation to the medium pH and the involvement of ionogenic groups using the potentiometric titration method (Figure 2). Analysis of the curves in Figure 2 shows that during all tests, the titration curves of the anionites decrease uniformly, indicating that they belong to the group of weakly basic anionites.

The presence of functional groups in the obtained anionites and the initial substances was confirmed by IR spectra. In the spectrum of the obtained anionite, absorption bands in the 650–900 cm^{-1} region are observed, which are associated with the vibrations of $=\text{NH}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$ groups, although the intensity of these bands is somewhat reduced. The absorption band at 840 cm^{-1} in the spectrum corresponds to para-substitution in the diphenylamine (DFA) ring. The absence of absorption bands in the 1670–1695 cm^{-1} region, which corresponds to the carbonyl group of furfural, indicates that furfural interacts with melamine and DFA through the aldehyde group [10].

The sorption of cations by the obtained anionites from solutions of copper, nickel, cobalt, zinc, sulfate, and cadmium chloride was studied under static conditions. To obtain information about the state of the ionogenic groups of the anionite and its anion exchange capacity, the effect of complex formation on the exchange capacity was utilized. As a model, the sorption of copper ions by the obtained anionite was used. Potentiometric titration curves were obtained both in the absence and in the presence of copper ions.

Figure 3 shows the potentiometric titration curves of the OH-form anionite without copper ions (first curve) and in the presence of copper ions (second curve). Comparison of these curves shows that complex formation does not affect the total exchange capacity of the anionite (the position of the inflection points in the titration curves remains unchanged). This can be explained by considering the reaction mechanism when copper ions that form complexes are either present or absent in the anionite [10].

Figure 3.
Potentiometric titration curves of the anionite

When the OH-form anionite comes into contact with NaCl and HCl solutions, the following reaction occurs:

In addition to NaCl and HCl solutions, when contacting solutions containing copper ions, an additional complex is formed, and after the first reaction it proceeds as follows:

Under the action of acids, this complex decomposes according to the following reaction:

Since the H–N bond is stronger than the Cu–N coordination bond [2], the acid capacity of the anionite does not change. This is because, in both cases, one H^+ ion corresponds to one amino

group. The proof of this is that the exchange capacity is the same in the first and second cases. It should be noted that under the experimental conditions, along with complex formation, a precipitation reaction also occurs:

This is confirmed by the acidification of the solution: in this case, the pH of the equilibrium solutions is significantly lower than that observed for ion exchange alone. The following pattern is observed: the greater the amount of precipitate formed, the lower the pH value of the equilibrium solutions. In this case, when a precipitate is formed, an increase in the amount of precipitate leads to a decrease in the potentiometric titration curve, while complex formation itself is not reflected in the shape of the potentiometric titration curve.

The initial course of the potentiometric curve is decisively influenced by the pH value: the more precipitate is released, the lower the titration curve. It should be noted that the formation of complex compounds with metal ions, in particular with copper, occurs at significantly lower pH values of the equilibrium solutions than precipitation. The maximum uptake of copper by the obtained anionite occurs when the pH of the equilibrium solutions is 3.5–4. With a further increase in the pH of the equilibrium solutions, the amount of precipitate increases, and copper sorption decreases to some extent due to complex formation. This is related to the fact that the formed precipitate hinders the diffusion of copper ions to the ionogenic groups of the anionite and adheres firmly to the anionite granules [11].

Sorption on ion exchangers is widely used in industrial practice for the recovery of molybdenum from various solutions obtained during the processing of low-grade raw materials, as well as for the removal of molybdenum from different types of water. In this context, the investigation of new, convenient, import-substituting sorbents with sufficiently high basicity and selective properties toward molybdenum and tungsten is of great interest. Therefore, in order to determine the applicability of the synthesized anionites in molybdenum hydrometallurgy, it is of interest to study the dependence of molybdenum ion sorption on various factors using the synthesized anionites. The use of melamine containing a triazine ring as a raw material, according to literature data, promotes the selective uptake of molybdenum ions by anionites.

Figure 4. Effect of solution pH on molybdenum sorption (g/l).
 1- synthesized anionite;
 2 - AN-2F anionite.

The results obtained for molybdenum sorption on the synthesized anionite were compared with data for industrial anionites AN-2F and FAN, which are recommended for the recovery of molybdenum from industrial solutions. An ammonium molybdate solution with a concentration of $C_{\text{initial}} = 1 \text{ g/l}$ was used as the model solution. The anionites were used in the OH^- , SO_4^{2-} , and Cl^- forms [12]. The obtained data show that molybdenum is better sorbed when the anionite is in the

chloride form in a pure ammonium molybdate solution. In the presence of competing sulfate ions (48 g/l SO_4^{2-}), the synthesized anionite exhibits higher selectivity toward molybdenum ions, and its sorption properties remain practically unchanged at $292\text{--}256 \text{ mg/g}$; the presence of competing ions reduces the sorption capacity by only $10\text{--}12\%$.

Conclusion

The effects of pH and the concentration of competing ions on molybdenum sorption were studied. The results of these investigations are presented in Figure 4, and for comparison, data for the AN-2F anionite are also shown [13]. Analysis of the curves in Figure 4 shows that the maximum sorption of molybdenum is observed in the pH range of $3.2\text{--}5.0$. Comparison of the data on molybdenum sorption by the synthesized anionite in the Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} forms indicates that, in the Cl^- form, molybdenum sorption is somewhat reduced due to anion exchange between chloride and sulfate ions. In the SO_4^{2-} form, this phenomenon is not observed [14]. Based on the obtained results, it should be noted that the synthesized anionite, due to its sorption properties, can be used in molybdenum hydrometallurgy for the purpose of molybdenum recovery.

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